

Integration Final Report of EUreka3D with the common European data space for cultural heritage

31/12/2024

Corresponding to D1.7 Integration Report 2

INFORMATION ON THE ACTION	
Grant Agreement N°	101100685 — EUreka3D — DIGITAL-2022-CULTURAL-02
Action Title	European Union's REKonstructed content in 3D
Action number	101100685
Project Call	DIGITAL-2022-CULTURAL-02

Author	Valentina Bachi and Antonella Fresa (Photoconsortium)
Contributors	Ignacio Lamata Martinez (EGI), Jolan Wuyts (EF), Hugo Manguinhas (EF)
Contact person	valentina.bachi@photoconsortium.net

Abbreviations

Consortium members

- INTERNATIONAL CONSORTIUM FOR PHOTOGRAPHIC HERITAGE (Photocons)
- TECHNOLOGIKO PANEPISTIMIO KYPROU (CUT)
- AYUNTAMIENTO DE GIRONA (CRDI)
- BIBRACTE
- MUSEO DELLA CARTA DI PESCIA
- STICHTING EUROPEANA (EF)
- STICHTING EGI (EGI)
- AGH AKADEMIA GORNICZO-HUTNICZA IM. STANISLAWA STASZICA W KRAKOWIE (AGH)
- INTERUNIVERSITAIR MICRO-ELECTRONICA CENTRUM (imec)

Other

AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
CHIs	Cultural Heritage Institutions
DS AGG	Data space aggregators
EAF	Europeana Aggregators' Forum
EDM	Europeana Data Model
ECBF	Europeana Capacity Building Framework
EIF	Europeana Impact Framework
ELF	Europeana Licensing Framework
ENA	Europeana Network Association
EPF	Europeana Publishing Framework
IIIF	International Image Interoperability Framework

Please see the [glossary available on Europeana Pro](#) for more formal definitions of terms used frequently.

Introduction

This report is written by the EUreka3D project partners with a special role for the Coordinator Photoconsortium, EGI as provider of the e-infrastructure that is hosting the EUreka3D services and Europeana Foundation, the organisation leading the deployment of the common European data space for cultural heritage under a contract with the European Union. The integration report template was discussed and approved by the Commission (HaDEA and DGConnect).

This report presents the project outcomes per specific area of data space deployment and is organised in four sections: 1. Technical integration into the data space infrastructure, 2. Integration of high-quality data, 3. Capacity building and fostering reuse, and 4. Digital services for the public.

The integration report is submitted in two phases: an initial version in month 6 of the project (i.e. D1.2) and the final version in the last month of the Action (i.e. this document, delivered in month 24).

This final integration report describes the outcomes of the EUreka3D project as integrated into the common European data space for cultural heritage. It presents the work done to achieve the Action's expected outcomes in a timely and smooth manner.

The final integration report also certifies the compliance of the project outcomes with the data space frameworks, and the quality requirements of published data according to the Europeana Publishing Framework. It is worth mentioning that in the EUreka3D project, quality assurance was an important element of the implementation plan. The quality of provided data from the digitisation action is aligned with the recommendations of the VIGIE 2020/654 Study on quality in 3D digitisation of tangible cultural heritage, and partner CUT provided guidance and quality controls on the digitisation done by the other content providers. In terms of quality of the metadata, the workflows of the EUreka3D Data Hub include a metadata input form based on the Europeana Data Model that also implements the use of LOD vocabularies, which are an important element for higher metadata tiers according to EPF.

This document corresponds to the EUreka3D Deliverable D1.7 *"Final Integration Report"* and complements the Deliverable D1.6 *"Final Technical report"*. Both documents are means of verification for the project's Milestone 4 "Final reporting".

1. Technical integration into the data space infrastructure

This section shows the integration of technical outcomes with the data space infrastructure, in particular with Europeana infrastructure and services, aggregation systems (such as Metis, Metis sandbox and Data Statistics Dashboard) and Europeana APIs. Underlying all of these products is the infrastructure to host, monitor, and recover systems.

All technical outcomes must comply with the following Europeana Guidelines: Europeana Development Guidelines¹ and Europeana Playbook for software development and integration².

BRIEF INTRODUCTION TO THE INTEGRATION SCENARIO

EUreka3D deployed a cloud-based environment for the Cultural Heritage sector, using cloud technology to provide high quality holistically enriched content to Europeana.

For this, an integration between EUreka3D and the Europeana systems took place on three layers with different scopes:

- Metadata and paradata for the technical aggregation of collections
- A 3D viewer to support visualisation of the 3D assets
- An Authentication and authorisation infrastructure.

The development of the so-called EUreka3D Data Hub, widely described in deliverables D3.2 and D3.3 took place in an iterative workflow process, in which all stakeholders participated: content providers identified the requirements and tested the tools, technical partners developed the cloud-based environment and tools to be compatible with Europeana frameworks, and finally Photoconsortium, as accredited aggregator of Europeana, worked in close collaboration with Europeana itself to enable the aggregation pipeline of datasets to be finalised.

The scopes and the integration plan for each of the three elements are provided below.

1. Technical aggregation of collections

Scope

A short description of the outcome: Metadata of the high-quality 3D digitised assets are made available via the OAI-PMH of the EUreka3D Data Hub for the Europeana Metis tool to harvest and then allow publication on europeana.eu. In addition to the metadata fields foreseen in the Europeana Data Model, that meet the requirements of the Europeana Publishing Framework (minimum tier B according to the Grant Agreement), the metadata

¹ <https://github.com/europeana/europeana-dev-guides>

² https://drive.google.com/file/d/12h1O6OLDawoua1pWHlsg5_EI0D12k7T5/view?usp=sharing

schema adopted in EUreka3D, while based on EDM, accommodates additional relevant information relating to the 3D objects (such as a direct download link to the RAW files of the 3D model and the paradata report produced by the content provider, and automated addition of LOD links from vocabularies). Currently, not all the information provided via the EUreka3D Data Hub is made visible in the Europeana portal, especially the metadata fields of the *edm:WebResource* class. It is expected that the expansion of EDM, currently under revision by the 3D working group in the Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage (hereafter referred to as 'the data space'), will enable the visualisation of these additional fields that exist in the metadata but are not shown to Europeana users. The additional metadata and links to paradata are available in the API results of the EUreka3D cultural heritage objects, made available through Europeana's API suite for anyone who wishes to reuse this information.

Main partners: EF, EGI, AGH, CUT, Photocons, imec

Integration scenario:

The project collaborated with EUDAT B2HANDLE to assign PIDs to the published 3D objects.

Content providers made use of storage and data/metadata management facilities in the EUreka3D environment to prepare the 3D datasets for publication in Europeana, according to the Europeana Data Model. In particular, a metadata input form allows content providers to manually create an XML file in EDM that is validated by the system and published on the OAI server for harvesting by Europeana. Other systems for creating XML, such as via API or by copying an existing XML in the EUreka3D Data Hub, have been tested and made available.

The project created an aggregation pipeline specific for 3D collections, while using MINT as planned for the aggregation of other types of objects. EUreka3D's custom solution creates a user-friendly and direct pipeline for any data provider that wants to store, aggregate and publish 3D cultural heritage to Europeana. The work delivered in the EUreka3D Data Hub serves to create a single pipeline for 3D, including storage, visualisation, metadata/paradata management and aggregation via OAI, thus creating a direct entry point to Europeana for 3D collections. As foreseen in the original plan, the project used also the MINT mapping and aggregation tool operated by the accredited aggregator Photoconsortium for other types of objects offered by some providers, such as images and text. In both cases (aggregation via EUreka3D for 3D, and aggregation via MINT for other object types), harvesting from an OAI-PMH server happened via the Metis tool, also using the Metis Sandbox to test the objects and their technical and quality compliance.

In addition, it is worth mentioning that the EUreka3D Data Hub integrates the possibility of allocating PIDs to the published objects. This was made possible thanks to the collaboration with EUDAT B2HANDLE³. While at the moment the PIDs can be shown in Europeana as *dc:identifier*, more work will take place in the context of the Data Space for Cultural Heritage project to enable a more effective implementation of the PIDs in the EDM metadata. Using B2HANDLE persistent identifiers ensures the sustainability of these identifiers in Europeana, allowing for better linking and a more stable connection between the published items on europeana.eu and the same objects in the Data Hub storage.

Deviation (yes/no) - no

³ <https://www.eudat.eu/services/userdoc/b2handle>

Integration plan

Stage	Details	Delivery date	Status	Responsible partner and role
Requirement collection	Collection of requirements needed to design the system, and explore possible solutions for the use cases concerning Europeana.	Requirements collected in multiple sessions. Informal versions created iteratively. Final version published in D3.3.	Completed	EGI , lead All partners involved
Metadata and paradata	Agreement on the metadata and paradata to be released to Europeana, based on the Europeana Data Model (EDM).	By M12	Completed	EGI / AGH , technical advisor CUT / Photocons , content advisor EF , Europeana advisor
Mapping to EDM and aggregation to Europeana	Use of MINT tool to perform the mapping of content providers' metadata to EDM and to expose the mapped datasets via OAI-PMH for harvesting by Metis	By M22	Completed Mapping of 3D objects was done through the newly created Data Hub, 2D objects were mapped through MINT.	Photocons , accredited aggregator All content providers involved EF , Metis operator

2. Eureka3D viewer

Scope
<p>A short description of the outcome:</p> <p>Europeana delegates the visualisation of 3D objects to the external providers chosen by the content provider. A 3D viewer is included in the Eureka3D cloud-based environment to allow the display of high-quality 3D digitised assets captured during the project on Europeana. This viewer has been created using an open-access library which offered the occasion to learn valid lessons and share knowledge within the consortium and with external experts who collaborated on the project.</p> <p>The viewer is accessible on europeana.eu through an oEmbed endpoint. oEmbed is an open format and a best practice to allow embedded content from one Website on other platforms. This allows the extensibility of the viewer on platforms other than europeana.eu, which is an important prerequisite to enable the possibilities of a decentralised data space.</p>
<p>Main partner: EGI, AGH, EF</p>
<p>Integration scenario:</p> <p>Eureka3D technical partners liaised with the Europeana Service Engagement team to configure Eureka3D's oEmbed in the europeana.eu frontend. CORS⁴ issues were addressed to allow the viewer to be rendered on the item page of europeana.eu.</p>
<p>Deviation No</p>

Integration plan				
Stage	Details	Delivery date	Status	Responsible partner and role
Requirement collection	Collection of requirements needed to design the system, and explore possible solutions for the use cases concerning Europeana.	Requirements collected in multiple sessions. Informal versions created iteratively. Final version published in D3.3.	Completed	EGI, lead All partners involved

⁴ Cross-Origin Resource Sharing

3D visualisation	Development of mechanisms to visualise the 3D assets generated by the Eureka3D content providers in the project. Creation of the oEmbed endpoint for embedding into Europeana	First version by M12 Final version by M20	Completed	EGI / AGH , developer EF , developer
Integration via oEmbed for enabling visualisation of 3D assets in Europeana portal	Configuration of the oEmbed endpoint and integration with Europeana	By M22	Completed	EGI / AGH , developer EF , developer

3. Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure

Scope

A short description of the outcome:

The EUreka3D cloud-based environment includes an identity management system (EGI Check-in), which enables authentication and authorisation mechanisms to be used in the project to access the infrastructure resources. Different groups of users have been defined, according to the permissions that have to be granted to them on the system. This possibility of granting different permissions to different groups of users according to the will of the content owner also allows for enabling collaborative projects between CHIs.

Main partner: EGI, AGH, EF

Integration scenario:

The EGI Check-in service protects EUreka3D resources. Each CHI participating in EUreka3D is assigned and represented by a distinctive group, which enables the configuration of different authorisation rules. The data owner can establish these rules, allowing the configuration of read and modify permissions on the data. Users coming from Europeana do not need to authenticate themselves, as the information and data published in Europeana are public and freely accessible. Similarly, information published through OAI-PMH is publicly available, so it is not necessary to authenticate the Europeana systems.

The Authentication and Authorisation infrastructure is a standalone component of the EUreka3D Data Hub based on the EGI federated identity providers, which could be of interest for future integration in Europeana: for example with the integration of Europeana's Single Sign-On service as a new identity provider to the Data Hub Check-In service, allowing users to use their Europeana account to authenticate themselves to Data Hub.

Deviation No

Integration plan

Stage	Details	Delivery date	Status	Responsible partner and role
Requirement collection	Collection of requirements needed to design the system, and explore possible solutions for the use cases concerning Europeana.	Requirements collected in multiple sessions. Full description can be found in D3.2. .	Completed	EGI , lead All partners involved
Authentication and Authorisation prototype	EGI Check-in is implemented for use in EUreka3D Data Hub by CHIs, as well as for demonstration and testing	By M6	Completed	EGI , developer
Study on the Europeana identity provider integration	Explore the possibility of integration of Europeana idP in the EGI Check-in ecosystem, to enable the integration with EOSC AAI.	By M24	Completed	EF , developer EGI , advisor

2. Integration of high-quality data

This section shows high-quality, usable and accessible data that the project will deliver to the data space supporting local and regional representation as well as multilingual accessibility.

All data outcomes must comply with the following Europeana Guidelines: Europeana Data Model⁵, Europeana Publishing Framework⁶, Europeana Content Strategy⁷, Guidance for Projects Partners doing Annotations, Transcriptions & Subtitles⁸.

Content and metadata

This section reports a clear content aggregation plan as well as the content provider, content and metadata Tiers, and expected publication date.

	Dataset ID	N. records	Type of media (image, sound, text, 3D, video)	Content Tier ⁹ (Tier 2, Tier 3, Tier 4)	Metadata Tier ¹⁰ (Tier A, Tier B, Tier C)	Copyright status ¹¹	Expected delivery date	Status	Link to Europeana
Content Provider: CUT									
New records							-		
Newly digitised records	1268	5	3D	Tier 4	Tier B	CC BY-SA	Delivery by M22	Published M23	Link This collection includes also 2 objects provided by Medelhavsmuseet, digitised and published by CUT as intermediate provider
Total records		5	3D	Tier 4	Tier B	CC BY-SA			
Content Provider: CRDI									
New records									

⁵ <https://pro.europeana.eu/page/edm-documentation>

⁶ <https://pro.europeana.eu/post/publishing-framework>

⁷ <https://pro.europeana.eu/post/europeana-content-strategy>

⁸ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1vDT7lppoPKbg0_y8ys_vE4OibYRHke1WKsNq1mR8fQ/edit?usp=sharing

⁹ https://pro.europeana.eu/files/Europeana_Professional/Publications/Publishing_Framework/Europeana_publishing_framework_content.pdf

¹⁰ https://pro.europeana.eu/files/Europeana_Professional/Publications/Publishing_Framework/Europeana_publishing_framework_metadata_v-0-8.pdf

¹¹ <https://pro.europeana.eu/page/available-rights-statements>

Newly digitised records	1280	50	3D	Tier 4	Tier B	PDM	Delivery by M22	Published M23	Link
Total records		50	3D	Tier 4	Tier B	PDM			
Content Provider: BIBRACTE									
New records	1278	10	3D (ground models)	Tier 4	Tier B	Open access	Delivery by M22	Published M23	Link
Newly digitised records	1278	261	3D (artefacts)	Tier 4	Tier B	Open access	Delivery by M22	Published M23	Link
New records		233	IMAGE (orthophotographs of terrains)	Tier 4	Tier B	Open access	Delivery in M24	In publication	
Total records		504	3D and IMAGE	Tier 4	Tier B	CC BY-SA			
Content Provider: MUSEO DELLA CARTA									
New records	1011	5.286	IMAGE and TEXT (documents)	Tier 4	Tier C	CC BY	Delivery by M22	Published M23	Link
Newly digitised records	1226	2	3D (paper moulds)	Tier 4	Tier C	CC BY	Delivery by M22	Published M23	Link
Total records		5.288	IMAGE, TEXT and 3D	TIER 4	Tier C	CC BY			

This aggregation work has resulted in the publication of:

- 328 high-quality 3D models
- 5.519 high-quality 2D cultural heritage objects¹²

All content ingested through Eureka3D is Content tier 4, and metadata Tier B+. All content ingested through Eureka3D is CC BY-SA or more openly licensed.

¹² Data already including the 233 images by Bibracte in publication

The EUreka3D project has also worked with local cultural heritage institutions that wanted to add content to Europeana through the EUreka3D Data Hub. These new collections have been provided as part of the EUreka3D project, without any of these partners being part of the EUreka3D consortium.

	Dataset ID	N. records	Type of media (image, sound, text, 3D, video)	Content Tier ¹³ (Tier 2, Tier 3, Tier 4)	Metadata Tier ¹⁴ (Tier A, Tier B, Tier C)	Copyright status ¹⁵	Expected delivery date	Delivery	Link to Europeana
Content Provider: INSPA (Girona City Council)									
New records	1262	5	3D	Tier 4	Tier B	PDM		Published M23	Link
Total records		5	3D	Tier 4	Tier B	PDM			
Content Provider: RAMS (Regionaal Archeologisch Museum a/d Schelde)									
New records	1261	16	3D	Tier 4	Tier B/C	CC BY		Published M23	Link
Total records		16	3D	Tier 4	Tier B/C	CC BY			
Content Provider: GENCAT (Generalitat de Catalunya)									
New records	1275	1	3D	Tier 4	Tier B	CC BY		Published M23	Link
Total records		1	3D	Tier 4	Tier B	CC BY			

Enrichments

The EUreka3D Data Hub, via the user interface of the metadata input form, automatically provides links to Getty AAT vocabularies, thus delivering enriched records for Europeana ingestion.

Validation of the enrichments

No further enrichments of objects were planned in this project.

¹³https://pro.europeana.eu/files/Europeana_Professional/Publications/Publishing_Framework/Europeana_publishing_framework_content.pdf

¹⁴https://pro.europeana.eu/files/Europeana_Professional/Publications/Publishing_Framework/Europeana_publishing_framework_metadata_v-0-8.pdf

¹⁵<https://pro.europeana.eu/page/available-rights-statements>

3. Capacity building and fostering reuse

This section shows the integration of all technical and training outcomes that strengthen the capacity of cultural heritage professionals and reuse communities working with digital cultural heritage, in particular in education, research, tourism and the creative industries.

All outcomes must comply with the Guidelines for the development and delivery of training¹⁶, Please include known connections with existing training offers or training developed in other data space projects.

All training and capacity building resources are reported on in *D2.2. Report on training programme*.¹⁷

The training mentioned here is only the training that involves the European data space for cultural heritage.

Training outcomes

Outcome	Audience	Learning goals¹⁸	Expected publication or delivery date	Partners involved
Online and onsite events				
"3D in Cultural Heritage" Capacity building event in Roma and online	Cultural Institutions; researchers in 3D for cultural heritage; PhD students; other cultural professionals	<i>User is able to Remember / Understand / Apply / Analyse</i>	6th June 2023	Organised by Photoconsortium with participation of project partners, and associate partners
"Transforming heritage" Webinar series in Autumn 2023 and 2024, a total of 6 online appointments dedicated to different topics	Cultural Institutions, archive sector, collections managers, Europeana network	<i>User is able to Remember / Understand / Apply / Analyse</i>	Series in 2023: 27/10/2023 10/11/2023 01/12/2023 Series in 2024: 26/9/2024 24/10/2024 15/11/2024	Photoconsortium in collaboration with ICA and with project partners
Paradata, Metadata and Data for 3D acquisition in	Digital Cultural Heritage community	<i>User is able to Remember /</i>	8 April and 17 May 2024	CUT

¹⁶ <https://pro.europeana.eu/page/guidelines-for-delivering-training-and-development>

¹⁷ Find the full deliverable for D2.2. here: <https://eureka3d.eu/deliverables-and-milestones/>

¹⁸ Please use Bloom's taxonomy for these learning goals. [See B.3 of the guidelines](#) mentioned above for more information

cultural heritage Webinar in two parts		<i>Understand / Apply / Analyse</i>		
Training session about the use of Europeana and its 3D objects Event in Bibracte	Teachers & educators	<i>User is able to Remember / Understand / Apply / Analyse / Evaluate</i>	27-29 November 2023	Bibracte
Training presentations for adopters of the EUreka3D tool and methods Event in Nancy	Cultural Institutions; researchers in 3D for cultural heritage, archaeologists	<i>User is able to Remember / Understand / Apply / Analyse / Evaluate / Create</i>	27 November 2024	Bibracte and associate partner Archéovision
Participation in Mnemosyne Summer School Training and presentation on 3D digitisation	Cultural Institutions; researchers in 3D for cultural heritage; other cultural professionals	<i>User is able to Remember / Understand / Apply / Analyse / Evaluate</i>	23-27 October 2023	CUT
EUreka3D: Preserving Values through #MemoryTwins Demo event	Project partners, heritage professionals education	<i>User is able to Remember / Understand / Apply / Analyse</i>	29 May 2024	CUT
“3D Heritage Innovators Exchange” Training Activity in Malta and in Cyprus	PhD students and professionals in heritage and archaeology	<i>User is able to Remember / Understand / Apply / Analyse / Evaluate / Create</i>	23-27 September 2024 (Malta) 5-7 December 2024 (Cyprus)	CUT
“EUreka3D Data Hub, implementing a Data Hub and services in the Data Space for Cultural Heritage” Demo event	Partners and members of the Advisory Board	<i>User is able to Remember / Understand / Apply / Analyse</i>	15 December 2023	EGI and CUT
EGI DataHub Webinar Demo event	Community of scientists in IT, data and e-infrastructures	<i>User is able to Remember / Understand / Apply / Analyse.</i>	11 September 2024	AGH with EGI
Training activity to visiting Mongolian students at CUT	PhD students in heritage and archaeology	<i>User is able to Remember / Understand /</i>	6-16 December 2024	CUT

		<i>Apply / Analyse / Evaluate / Create</i>		
Training workshop at EGI 2024 Participation in EGI conference	Technology/service providers; 3D digitisation and other cultural professionals	<i>User is able to Remember / Understand / Apply / Analyse</i>	30 September - 1 October 2024	EGI with CUT
Paradata, Metadata, and Data in 3D Digital Documentation for Cultural Heritage: #DigitalTwins or #MemoryTwins Training workshop at Euromed 2024	Cultural Institutions; researchers in 3D for cultural heritage; other cultural professionals; policy makers	<i>User is able to Remember / Understand / Apply / Analyse</i>	2 December 2024	CUT
Training action at Image & Research 2024 Participation in conference in Girona	Cultural Institutions; technology/service providers; 3D digitisation and other cultural professionals	<i>User is able to Remember / Understand / Apply / Analyse</i>	21 November 2024	CRDI with Photoconsortium
EUreka3D Final Conference	CHI professionals, researchers, and practitioners in Digital Cultural Heritage	<i>User is able to Remember / Understand / Apply / Analyse</i>	13 December 2024	CRDI
Training activity in Girona Workshop for Catalan CHIs	Cultural Institutions and professionals, technology/service providers	<i>User is able to Remember / Understand / Apply / Analyse / Evaluate</i>	13 December 2024	CRDI
Publications				
VIGIE Study 2020/654 materials "3D digitization guidelines Steps to Success" Booklet, plus flyers and postcards to explain the 3D digitisation recommendations in a more user-friendly way	Cultural Institutions; technology/service providers; 3D digitisation professionals	Users learn about the steps to be followed to achieve high quality 3D digitisation	Published in May 2024	CRDI with CUT, Photoconsortium, imec
Paradata, Metadata and Data in Digitisation	Digital Cultural Heritage community	Users learn about the state of the art in EU	Published December 2024	CUT

Open access publication with Springer		about progress in 3D digitisation and documentation		
Case studies on content providers' journey Online publication	Cultural Institutions; Europeana network	Users learn from peer CHIs on their digitisation journey, to take inspiration from	Website page available in September 2024	CRDI with collaboration of all the partners
EUreka3D Data Hub services and tools user manuals Online publication	Cultural Institutions; technology/service providers; researchers in cultural heritage; 3D digitisation and other cultural professionals	Users can see the EUreka3D Data Hub in action and learn how to use it, from joining the EUreka3D community to the publication of models in Europeana.	Website page + Iterative productions of User manual, version 3 was available in November 2024	EGI with AGH and imed
EUreka3D booklet Online publication + 200 printed copies	Cultural Institutions; technology/service providers; researchers in cultural heritage; 3D digitisation and other cultural professionals; policy makers	Users can discover all the stories, outcomes and available resources developed by EUreka3D project	11 December 2024	CRDI with collaboration of all partners

4. Digital services for the public

This section reports on the technical outcomes that contribute to the user experience on the Europeana website. It also covers editorial content delivered by the project such as blog posts, virtual exhibitions, and galleries.

Technical outcomes on Europeana.eu

Integration of EUreka3D viewer	Completed
A short description of the outcome	
The EUreka3D embedded viewer (example item page) was configured in Europeana by EF's Service Experience team so 3D models could be embedded and viewed from within the Europeana item page.	
Main partner EGI	
Integration scenario (A/B/C) Integration Scenario C will be followed. Europeana will maintain the configuration of the embedded viewer for as long as the viewer stays online, correctly displays 3D models, and does not impede the performance or user experience of europeana.eu	
Deviation no	

Editorial outcomes

These outcomes must comply with the following Guidelines: Europeana Editorial Guidelines¹⁹ and Europeana Pro Guide²⁰.

Title	Type	Main contributing partner	Publication date	Languages	total unique visits on 10/12/2024
History of 3D	Blog	Photocons	09/08/2023	EN, ES, IT	1404
Optical Views	Blog	CRDI	25/10/2023	EN, ES, IT	614
Bibracte, a 2000-year-old town under a forest	Blog	Bibracte	11/01/2024	FR,EN	1655
EUreka3D project page	Pro	All	14/11/2022	EN	1280
VIGIE Study	Pro	CUT	14/04/2023	EN	684
Discover how the EUreka3D project supports 3D in the data space for cultural heritage	Pro	All	16/01/2023	EN	543

¹⁹ <https://pro.europeana.eu/discover-the-data/creating-editorial>

²⁰ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1HBnbDYxqgZ7-nEcfK93pwoZlCf6vz3Q-Yw_6ndDpgoE/edit

Famous monuments in 3D	Gallery	EF	01/09/2023	EN	204
3D archaeological treasures	Gallery	EF	01/09/2023	EN	181
3D Wonders	Gallery	EF	01/09/2023	EN	164
Bibracte	Gallery	Bibracte	11/01/24	EN, FR	163
Fikardou Village	Pro	CUT	28/05/24	EN	175
Bibracte Jozef Wilczek	Pro	Bibracte	11/06/24	EN	168
The Magic Lantern	Blog	CRDI	07/08/2024	EN, ES, IT	581
Pescia Museum	Blog	MdC	05/09/2024	EN, ES, IT	638
Lambousa	Blog	CUT	01/10/2024	EN	92
Looting and trafficking	Gallery	Bibracte	15/07/2024	EN, FR	80
Magic lanterns from Girona city museum	Gallery	Photocons	27/11/2024	EN	30
Heritage cameras and heritage photographers	Gallery	Photocons	27/11/2024	EN	49
Flavours of Cyprus	Gallery	Photocons	27/11/2024	EN	52
Paper Moulds from MdC	Gallery	EF	10/10/2024	EN	36
Modern art from MdC	Gallery	EF	10/10/2024	EN	54
Cameras, lanterns, and more pre-cinema 3D heritage from Girona	Gallery	Photocons	12/12/2024	EN	Published after stats collection
The Oppidum of Bibracte: A Thriving Economic Center	Gallery	Bibracte	12/12/2024	EN, FR	Published after stats collection
Daily Life of the Inhabitants of the Oppidum of Bibracte	Gallery	Bibracte	12/12/2024	EN, FR	Published after stats collection
Animals on the Oppidum of Bibracte	Gallery	Bibracte	12/12/2024	EN, FR	Published after stats collection
The Dishware of the Oppidum of Bibracte	Gallery	Bibracte	12/12/2024	EN, FR	Published after stats collection
EUreka3D wrap-up post	Pro	EF	12/12/2024	EN	Published after stats collection
Digital Media Authenticity	Pro	imec	18/12/2024	EN	Published after stats collection
TOTAL UNIQUE VISITS					8847²¹

²¹ Due to a data loss event at Europeana in mid-2024 some user data statistics over a period of 2 weeks have been lost. The true number of unique visits to europeana.eu links, including editorial for EUreka3D, is therefore likely (slightly) higher than what is being reported here.

ADDENDUM:

In addition to the publication of Blogs, Pro blogs and Galleries on Europeana platform, the project used two other important channels of online publication, which contributed to the provision of digital services to the public:

- The project [website](#) that clearly indicates the liaison with Europeana. With dedicated pages showcasing project progress and outcomes such as the Capacity Building and the Resources pages, the Case Studies, and the outcomes of the Final Conference including recordings and the Final Booklet contributed to the promotion of Europeana.
- The project [blog hosted on Digitalmeetsculture.net](#), which was regularly updated with posts about the work of the project, the announce of the Capacity Building events, the new collections made available in Europeana and the editorials which were published. With over 70 posts published at the time of writing (December 2024), the blog offered an additional visibility to Europeana and the common European data space for cultural heritage.

Social media promotion was also regularly performed in close collaboration with Europeana.